

NFDI4Earth

Milestone MS1.3.5

Modular NFDI4Earth-ready course materials published under an open license

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Executive summary

The report offers a detailed overview of the NFDI4Earth Education and Training services progress and future plans in creating and sharing modular course materials for Earth System Data Science. It describes the systematic approach used to develop and publish Open Educational Resources through the NFDI4Earth Educational Portal (EduPortal) platform, integrating them into our catalog of educational resources and making them more widely accessible through the NFDI4Earth KnowledgeHub and OneStop4All. The report also covers the technical infrastructure supporting the EduPortal and provides an overview of its functionality. It includes a comprehensive list of the current course offerings available on the EduPortal and outlines upcoming plans for course offering expansions and functionality improvements.

Abbreviations

CC - Creative Commons

CC0 - Creative Commons Zero

EduPilots - Educational Pilots

EduPortal - NFDI4Earth Educational Portal

EduTrain - NFDI4Earth Education and Training team

ESS - Earth System Science

KH - Knowledge Hub

LMS - Learning Management System

LTI - Learning Tools Interoperability

MOOC - Massive Open Online Course

NFDI - National Research Data Infrastructure

NFDI4Earth - National Research Data Infrastructure for Earth System Science

OERs - Open Educational Resources

OS4A - One Stop 4 All

RDM - Research Data Management

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1. Introduction

The NFDI4Earth project [1] is committed to supporting the Earth System Sciences (ESS) community by providing them with the necessary tools and knowledge to manage and analyse their research data effectively. Through its Education and Training team (EduTrain), the project is developing a wide range of training materials and services specifically tailored to the needs of the ESS community, all of which are available under open licenses. These resources are designed to assist researchers in the ESS to conduct open, reproducible research.

EduTrain's efforts include providing and maintaining a catalogue of Open Educational Resources (OER) related to Earth System Sciences (ESS) topics to make existing offerings easily accessible to NFDI4Earth users, developing a curriculum to structure the knowledge required for open and reproducible research in ESS, and publishing open educational materials that cover this knowledge. Furthermore, EduTrain provides guidelines and best practices for users interested in sharing their educational content through NFDI4Earth channels, in addition to offering financial support via Educational Pilots [2].

This report will primarily focus on how we conceptualised and constructed a learning environment to develop and publish courses and the current course offerings. In the following sections, we will explore the process of building the learning environment, the courses we have developed and published so far, and our plans for future work.

2. NFDI4Earth Educational Portal

The NFDI4Earth Educational Portal (EduPortal), operating on the Open edX platform [3], is a virtual learning environment where modular courses curated by EduTrain are published. This section will explore the target audience of our courses, our content inventory and content structure, the technical infrastructure of EduPortal, course authoring for EduPortal, and our plans for maintenance and update.

2.1. Target Audience

The primary target audience for the educational resources and services provided by EduTrain is researchers, encompassing individuals at all career stages, from early-career researchers such as PhD students and postdoctoral fellows to established senior scientists and professors. However, our scope extends beyond the research community, aiming to reach a broader range of stakeholders within the ESS domain. This includes educators responsible for teaching ESS-related subjects, professionals involved in training and development programs, and university students pursuing studies in various ESS disciplines.

Addressing the diverse needs of such a varied target audience presents a significant challenge. To effectively reach and engage with these distinct groups, EduTrain employs a multifaceted approach, leveraging various tools and platforms to disseminate its educational resources. This ensures that the content and delivery methods are tailored to the specific requirements and preferences of each target group, maximising the impact and reach of the project's educational activities (see Technical Infrastructure).

2.2. Content Inventory and Structure

The content on EduPortal is derived from a blend of sources, including NFDI4Earth partners, EduTrain events, EduPilots, and the integration of OERs from the EduTrain catalogue. This catalogue houses educational materials developed by either expert individuals or well-known educational platforms, carefully chosen for their credibility, relevance, and the quality of their content. Individuals are distinguished academics and professionals who release content under open licenses on platforms like GitHub and YouTube. The educational platforms that consistently offer quality-controlled content, such as EarthLab [4], MIT OpenCourseWare [5], and TIB [6], are listed for regular automatic metadata harvesting, ensuring that the catalogue is continuously updated and expanded.

EduTrain has implemented a well-organised and adaptable curriculum to structure and modulates its courses. This curriculum is crafted to ultimately encompass essential knowledge points and learning pathways, focusing on FAIR data analysis and management within ESS using open and reproducible methods and tools. The current version of the curriculum includes a comprehensive range of subjects, from the fundamentals of spatial data analysis and management, such as spatial data formats, to advanced data analysis techniques, such as machine learning. Details are available in MS1.3.9 [7].

2.3. Technical Infrastructure

The most suitable platform for course publishing was selected based on the prioritisation of our objectives. While our long-term objective is to publish courses as FAIR digital objects, creating an environment that enables effective and accessible learning is a primary focus. At present, Learning Management Systems are considered to provide the best option for publishing courses in a user-friendly and interactive manner.

In our search for an LMS to serve as the foundation for EduPortal, we conducted a thorough evaluation of multiple options based on key criteria, including flexibility, scalability, support, and security. After careful consideration, we have chosen to use Open edX. Open edX is an open-source platform that offers enhanced user experience and provides the necessary

Figure 1: Open edX studio: Course authoring dashboard (top-left), Course structure and content organisation interface (top-right), Types of component for course creation (bottom-left), Advanced settings for adding interactive components (bottom-right)

infrastructure for the shift towards interactive and personalised learning experiences. Our selection process is detailed in D1.3.12 [8].

We employ the Open edX Tutor Instance, a Docker-based Open edX distribution that streamlines the deployment, customisation, and upgrades of the platform. This approach brings various advantages, including faster setup times, simplified maintenance, and improved reliability. Additionally, it supports a range of plugins to expand its functionality.

The content management system Open edX Studio, which is part of the Open edX platform, is used to author and manage courses. It offers educators and course authors an intuitive interface for creating, organising, and publishing course content. The Studio incorporates drag-and-drop interfaces, pre-designed templates for course structures, and seamless integration with various multimedia tools, facilitating the dissemination of rich content to students. Furthermore, it enables the management of course schedules and facilitates the tracking of student progress. Its advanced features encompass video lectures, quizzes, discussion forums, peer-to-peer social learning, and machine-graded and peer-graded assignments, making it a popular choice among academic institutions and organisations worldwide (Fig. 1).

The LMS in Open edX is the core component where learners interact with the course content and where course delivery takes place. It is the interface that students use to access course materials, participate in activities, and track their progress, and it serves as the foundation of

Figure 2: Open edX LMS: NFDI4Earth educational portal (left), Course content and lesson delivery (right)

our course delivery (Fig. 2).

Login mechanisms are essential for maintaining security, functionality, and personalisation of the EduPortal. A robust login system is crucial for creating a secure, personalised, and interactive educational environment. We offer an academic login option to enhance security and improve user experience. This option streamlines the login process for users and facilitates seamless integration with institutional systems (Fig. 3).

We provide interactive Jupyter notebooks, which are essential for working with data, allowing students to engage in hands-on learning without facing installation barriers or dealing with insufficient computational power. Integrating interactive Jupyter notebooks into the Open edX platform provides an environment where students can write, run, and visualise code in real-time and facilitate the immediate application of theoretical concepts. This integration, using Learning Tools Interoperability (LTI), enhances student engagement, motivation, and understanding by providing dynamic content and instant feedback on coding exercises (Fig. 4).

The courses are set to be self-paced, enabling users to learn at their own speed. The

Figure 3: Academic ID login

Figure 4: Interactive Jupyter Notebook integrated as an advanced module

EduPortal does not mandate users to complete any compulsory prerequisites to enrol in a course. However, recommended prerequisites are provided in the metadata displayed on the course home pages. These prerequisites are associated with courses that can offer the required knowledge; if such courses are not available, the subject becomes a priority in the development of new EduTrain courses. Courses typically consist of modules, and completion of a module is not obligatory before progressing to the next one. This allows users to plan their own learning paths to achieve their educational objectives, whether through the assistance of the NFDI4Earth curriculum or independently.

To ensure publishing our courses adheres to the FAIR principles, we have implemented several key features that enhance both discoverability and usability. The courses available on the EduPortal are automatically harvested and integrated into the EduTrain catalogue of OERs. This process ensures that our courses are readily available within the KnowledgeHub. The KnowledgeHub's SPARQL endpoint allows these courses to be easily found and accessed for various applications. However, the KnowledgeHub interface can be overwhelming for users who are not familiar with SPARQL. To improve upon this, the OneStop4All (OS4A) platform enhances the user experience by offering the EduTrain catalogue in an interactive and intuitive format. This user-friendly interface enables users to browse through the courses and interact with them and provides direct access to the EduPortal, simplifying the process of discovering and using our courses. Following the NFDI4Earth approach in providing both the OS4A platform focused on user experience and KnowledgeHub for more advanced users, we in EduTrain have extended the reach and utility of the content in the EduPortal by making the course materials available on GitLab. While our educational portal offers a structured environment for learning, providing access to the source materials on GitLab empowers educators and learners to tailor the content to their specific needs, enhancing flexibility and promoting collaborative development. Each course on the EduPortal has its own GitLab repository linked to the course homepage, allowing for convenient download and broad community reuse. These repositories house material, course curriculum, and course metadata (Fig. 5).

2.4. Design Process

We have put in our best effort to create a positive user experience and ensure that EduPortal effectively meets its goals. We aimed to develop a visually appealing, functional, user-friendly, and effective platform to achieve its objectives. We researched different methods to guide the development of our educational platform. The design principles below demonstrate our approach to developing a design for EduPortal that enhances user experience and accessibility.

Web design research underscores the significance of harmonising the design with users' mental models, defined as their perceptions about a system. This synchronisation promotes efficient interaction. By capitalising on users' pre-existing knowledge, designers can craft user-friendly

Figure 5: Integration of EduPortal courses into different platforms for enhanced discoverability

interfaces that necessitate minimal learning, ultimately enhancing user engagement and goal attainment [9]. This approach highlights the importance of employing familiar design patterns; therefore, we drew inspiration from reputed e-learning websites such as edX [10] and Coursera [11] to reduce cognitive load and enable users to concentrate on their learning objectives rather than grappling with the interface. Research shows that web users typically scan rather than read web pages thoroughly [12]. To improve the visibility and accessibility of key information, we structured our courses and their content with a coherent and well-organised content format.

The principle of minimalism in design is crucial, particularly for maintaining users' attention and promoting deeper engagement with the website [13], [14]. This is especially important for learning platforms, where a non-distracting environment can significantly enhance the quality of learning [15]. We tried to develop distinct yet simple design elements to help make the EduPortal memorable and speed up loading times, which is essential for maintaining user interest and reducing bounce rates. The EduPortal has been designed with a blue colour scheme, a choice often linked with traits such as trust, security, and professionalism, as research indicates [16].

Relying on these design principles to create the initial Mockups for the EduTrain homepage, the EduPortal homepage, course homepages, user area, and course navigation. These designs are still in the draft stage and will be refined to ensure alignment with the evolving NFDI4Earth products (Fig. 6).

Figure 6: Structure of the EduTrain homepage (left) and the EduPortal homepage (right)

Figure 7: Structure of the course homepages (left), the user area (middle), and the course navigation(right)

2.5. Course Authoring

The [guidelines](#) for preparing course material for the EduPortal are available on NFDI4Earth GitLab. This living document is continuously updated to align with the evolving portal. It covers various topics such as the EduTrain metadata schema, templates for different Creative Commons licenses (CC licenses), course settings, modular course design recommendations, content formats, and adding various types of content to the EduPortal. While the portal and its content are public, publishing content on the portal is restricted. Educators interested in accessing the guidelines and the course authoring page must agree to basic terms and conditions (see sec. A), committing to providing proper credits and metadata for FAIR publication through the NFDI4Earth channels and using open licenses.

Open licensing is a critical factor in facilitating reusability. Various open licenses can be used with OERs, with Creative Commons being the most commonly utilised. Creative Commons offers a suite of free licenses, ranging from the most liberal, CC0, which waives all rights and places the work in the public domain, to the most restrictive, CC BY-NC-ND, which permits others to use the work but not adapt it or use it for commercial purposes [17]. The Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license is the default license for all course modules. This licensing model provides preemptive permission grants, thus eliminating the need for individuals to seek permission each time they want to use or modify the materials, which is a common courtesy and a best practice. While the CC BY license is our primary choice, other Creative Commons licenses are employed when specified by the creators of the materials.

2.6. Maintenance and Update

Improving EduPortal continues to involve actively soliciting feedback from N4E partners and promoting the portal at major events, including the annual NFDI4Earth plenary and the EGU conference. Since its public release the EduPortal user base has steadily expanded, allowing for more comprehensive feedback collection. Feedback has now been gathered for multiple courses, notably “Image Processing and Analysis,” “Publishable NetCDF-Data Creation,” “Fundamentals of Spatial Data Mining and Machine Learning,” and “Python for Spatial Data Analysis.”

Active user feedback collection is ongoing. All significant user feedback and requests for features or corrections that could not be immediately implemented are systematically recorded as GitLab issues. This process ensures thorough tracking and timely resolution, facilitating a community-driven approach to EduPortal’s continual improvement. While most feedback has been positive, several insightful suggestions and constructive criticisms have proven especially valuable. Users have notably requested enhanced interactive notebooks, additional practical exercises, clearer course navigation, and the continued inclusion of dedicated feedback sections at the end of each course.

The EduPortal is expanding its course offerings by developing and publishing new course materials covering knowledge points and learning pathways established in the framework of the NFDI4Earth curriculum. We actively add new knowledge points and learning pathways to our curricula through collected feedback and by monitoring educational offerings for ESS inside and outside of NFDI4Earth. Another approach to expanding the concepts covered by our curriculum is to evaluate the connection between modules on the EduPortal that are not thematically covered by the NFDI4Earth curriculum, such as modular courses created by our EduPilots, and the current topics within the curriculum. This assessment leads to the definition of new learning pathways to expand our curriculum. Thus, the EduPortal remains synced with the rest of the EduTrain Services. This approach offers a two-way benefit: firstly, the NFDI4Earth curriculum guides the development of new courses and modules on the EduPortal, ensuring their relevance and value. Secondly, the content from the EduPortal, once aligned with NFDI4Earth FAIR and open standards, continuously enhances and expands the NFDI4Earth curriculum itself. In other words, it’s a synergistic relationship where both the EduPortal and the NFDI4Earth curriculum continuously improve and grow by leveraging each other’s strengths and content. Alignment of new courses with the curriculum involves mapping their content to existing concepts and identifying how they relate to and enhance the current framework. This process not only expands the curriculum but also strengthens the coherence and continuity of knowledge presented.

The NFDI4Earth curriculum is envisioned as an interconnected map of knowledge within Earth system sciences, where each course is part of a larger, continuous network of concepts. Rather

than viewing knowledge as discrete units, we emphasise the relationships between topics, showing how they connect and build upon each other. Not every course must belong to the curriculum, but our vision is to integrate courses that align with the NFDI4Earth mission into this interconnected framework. This allows for the creation of multiple learning pathways—or micro-curricula—tailored to individual learning goals. While we refer to “the” NFDI4Earth curriculum as a whole, it encompasses numerous pathways that learners can navigate based on their specific interests and needs. Essentially, the OERs and the EduPortal contribute high-quality content, and the NFDI4Earth curriculum offers the cohesive framework that ties everything together.

3. Courses Offerings

In addition to detailed course descriptions available on the EduPortal [18], this section gives an overview of our published and soon-to-be-published courses, which include::

- **Image Processing and Analysis:** Offered through a NFDI4Earth EduPilot, this course provides six modules on advanced techniques in image processing relevant to a variety of scientific applications, emphasising practical skills that can be directly applied in research.
- **How to Create Publishable NetCDF-Data:** This course, sourced from educational events, consists of six modules that guide learners through the process of creating and analysing NetCDF datasets that meet publication standards, crucial for researchers dealing with large datasets.
- **Introduction to Python:** Available in the NFDI4Earth catalogue, this extensive 16-module course introduces Python programming, focusing on applications in data science and earth sciences to equip researchers with essential coding skills.
- **Python for Spatial Data Analysis:** Derived from educational events, this 11-module course dives into Python applications for spatial data analysis, emphasising using open, reproducible data analysis methods.
- **Introduction into Chunking for Large Gridded Datasets:** A four-module course from a NFDI4Earth EduPilot that teaches techniques for managing and analysing large gridded datasets, which is increasingly important in fields like climatology and oceanography.
- **Fundamentals of Spatial Data Mining and Machine Learning:** This NFDI4Earth EduPilot course offers four modules that cover the basics of data mining and machine learning, tailored for spatial data applications.
- **Fundamentals of Spatial Data Formats for Earth Data Science:** Currently under development, this course will provide six modules on key data types and formats used in earth sciences, enhancing data handling skills.
- **Introduction to Open Reproducible Science:** This three-module course from the NFDI4Earth catalogue teaches principles and practices of open science, aiming to foster

reproducibility and transparency in research.

- **Fundamentals of Big Spatial Data:** This twelve-module course provides essential techniques and practical tools for managing, analysing, and interpreting large-scale spatial datasets, specifically tailored for applications in geoinformatics and Earth system science.
- **Image Pre-processing, Feature Generation and Classification in Remote Sensing:** This eleven-module course from a NFDI4Earth EduPilot, still under development, will delve into specialised techniques for preprocessing and analysing remote sensing data.
- **Streamlining Atmospheric Science, Oceanography, Climate, and Water Research with Fortran-accelerated R:** Currently under development, this NFDI4Earth EduPilot course promises five modules designed to integrate Fortran with R for enhanced computational efficiency in environmental sciences.
- **Computational Tools in Climate Science:** This course, also from a NFDI4Earth EduPilot, offers 73 modules covering key computational approaches in climate science, from analysing climate datasets to exploring climate modelling, extremes detection, and AI-based climate impact assessments.
- **Python and Earth Observation Data:** This NFDI4Earth EduPilot course delivers eight modules on using Python and Earth Observation data to examine urban transformations, featuring techniques in flood detection, nighttime lights analysis, and air quality measurement.
- **Python and Volunteered Geographic Information:** This NFDI4Earth EduPilot course offers seven modules covering applied methodologies for spatial analysis using Python combined with Volunteered Geographic Information, focusing on building extraction, population analysis, and road network assessments.
- **Python and Social Media Geographic Information:** This NFDI4Earth EduPilot course offers four modules covering essential skills for retrieving and analysing location-based social media data using Python, enabling investigation of urban dynamics and patterns associated with significant societal events.
- **Python Basics for Artificial Intelligence:** This NFDI4Earth EduPilot course offers 13 modules covering foundational skills in Python programming necessary for artificial intelligence applications, covering essential libraries such as NumPy and Pandas through practical exercises designed to prepare participants for advanced AI and data science tasks.
- **Artificial Intelligence Basics and Geographical Applications:** This NFDI4Earth EduPilot course offers 11 modules covering fundamental concepts of artificial intelligence and machine learning, emphasising their applications in geographical contexts such as soil sealing classification, weather prediction, ship detection, and multiclass analysis using advanced neural network methods.

4. Future Work

Moving forward, regular maintenance and ongoing expansion of the EduPortal will be key to ensuring its continued relevance and usefulness. This will include frequent updates to content and the platform, prompt resolution of technical issues, and sustained improvement of the user experience. Periodic reviews of the curriculum and technological infrastructure will also be necessary to keep pace with emerging developments in Earth System Sciences and educational technology. Data analytics and user feedback will guide these enhancements, informing changes in user interface design, content delivery formats, and the integration of new topics and tools. Through these efforts, the EduPortal will remain a dynamic resource for the evolving needs of the ESS community.

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A. Terms and Conditions

Welcome to the NFDI4Earth Educational Portal (EduPortal), a platform dedicated to providing access to high-quality educational materials and tools that promote open and reproducible research methods. We are committed to providing our users with trusted and reliable service. We have established the following terms and conditions to ensure that our community benefits from a secure and efficient environment. By accessing and using our services, you acknowledge and agree to comply with these terms. Membership in the NFDI4Earth Educational Portal signifies your acceptance of these terms and conditions.

A.1. Using NFDI4Earth Educational Portal

EduPortal services are available to anyone interested in accessing Open Educational Resources (OERs) in Earth System Sciences (ESS). There are no restrictions on the use or reuse of the content, provided that users comply with the applicable open licenses and provide proper attribution as required by the specific content licenses.

A.1.1. Feedback

We appreciate your input, ideas, and feedback about the EduPortal. When you provide us with feedback, you grant us permission to use it without any restrictions. While we appreciate your input, NFDI4Earth reserves the right to use feedback, whether we were already aware of it, developed it ourselves, or received it from other sources.

A.1.2. Removal of Content

If any inappropriate content is identified on our Portal, please feel free to notify us at any time. While we will review requests for content removal, we are not obligated to fulfill the requests or provide direct responses.

A.1.3. Cookies

We use cookies on the NFDI4Earth Educational Portal to enhance user experience and enable some website functionalities.

A.2. Authoring Courses on NFDI4Earth Educational Portal

You must be an instructor affiliated with a German university to access our course authoring services. When registering as a course author, you are required to provide accurate, complete, and updated information. You must also adhere to the specified conditions in this document when using the EduPortal course authoring services.

A.2.1. Content Standards

Content must be factually accurate, up-to-date, and relevant to Earth System Sciences. Content must align with the educational objectives of NFDI4Earth, focusing on open and reproducible research methods. Content must adhere to high academic standards, including clarity, coherence, and rigor, and must be free from any form of plagiarism or unethical practices.

A.2.2. Metadata Requirements

Course authors must fill out the metadata form for each submission. Metadata should include but is not limited to title, subject, description, type, resources (authors), language, and rights.

A.2.3. Licensing Requirements

All content must be published under an open license to facilitate reuse and sharing. The default license is the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license. Course authors may choose other Creative Commons licenses. Licensing information must be included in the metadata provided for each submission.

A.2.4. Attribution

Course authors must ensure proper attribution for all third-party materials included in the submissions and comply with the licensing terms of those materials.

A.2.5. Ownership

Course authors retain ownership of the content. However, by submitting content, you grant EduPortal a non-exclusive, royalty-free license to use, reproduce, adapt, publish, and distribute your content within our services.

A.2.6. Review and Modification of Content

All content submissions are reviewed to ensure compliance with our quality and relevance standards. EduPortal reserves the right to accept, reject, or request modifications to any content submitted. EduPortal may modify the format or presentation of your content to fit the platform, and user needs better while maintaining the integrity of the content.

A.2.7. Rights and Responsibilities

Contributors are responsible for ensuring that their content complies with all applicable laws and regulations. By contributing, you absolve EduPortal and its affiliates of any resulting claims.

A.3. Violations

Users must not:

- Post content that involves or promotes illegal activities.
- Share content that poses threats or organizes real-world violent acts.
- Use the platform to harass or abuse others.
- Infringe on intellectual property, privacy, or other rights by distributing unauthorised content.
- Engage in spam or share irrelevant advertising or solicitation content.
- Violate any local, state, national, or international laws.
- Share passwords or grant unauthorised access to accounts.
- Attempt unauthorised access to other users' accounts.
- unauthorisedly tamper with or use non-public areas of our systems.
- Impersonate or misrepresent affiliation with any person or entity.
- Commit plagiarism or use unauthorised materials for content creation.

A.4. Termination and Changes

EduPortal reserves the right to remove any content or suspend or terminate your access to the platform for violating our terms. EduPortal also reserves the right to make changes to these terms at any time. Your continued use of the platform following any modifications indicates your acceptance of the revised terms.

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The content on EduPortal is provided “as-is” and “as-available.” While efforts are made to ensure accuracy and quality, no guarantees are made regarding the completeness, reliability, or suitability of the content for any purpose. EduPortal is not liable for any errors or omissions in the content or for any loss or damage resulting from the use or reliance on the content. Users are responsible for verifying the information and ensuring it meets their needs.

A.6. Contact Information

For any questions or concerns regarding these terms, please contact us at [EduTrain](#)